

Article

Collaborative Teaching Between Special Education Teachers and Mainstream Teachers in Inclusive Education

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Abstract:

This study investigates collaborative teaching between special education teachers. In schools, mainstream teachers incorporate inclusive education. The set of standardized questionnaires were used to conduct the survey. The study sample was selected through a technical universal sampling method that involved 19 teacher respondents, comprising special education teachers and mainstream teachers in selected public schools in Talisay City Division. Quantitative data were analyzed descriptively using frequency counts, percentages, a weighted mean, and a t-test. The findings show that special education teachers and mainstream teachers have a "Very Positive" perception toward collaboration in teaching for the readiness aspect (weighted mean = 3.39), and a medium level of attitude (weighted mean = 3.20). While there is no significant difference between the perceptions of SPED and mainstream teachers about collaboration in inclusive education, The findings suggest strengthening collaboration between Special education teachers (SPED) and mainstream teachers to increase effective teaching in inclusive education in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and readiness.

Keywords: Collaboration, Teaching, Special Education and Mainstream Teachers

Introduction

Humans' most important contribution to social progress is their ability to create new information, share and spread it among communities, and find new ways to use that information to make society better (Brem et al., 2021). Recently, COVID-19 has been a threat to health around the world for more than two years, and teachers are leaving schools and students are having a hard time adjusting (Agaton & Cueto, 2021). Byrd & Alexander (2020) emphasized that special education teachers and regular education teachers started working together during and post pandemic to improve their skills and knowledge and figure out how to

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better teach students with special educational needs (LSEs) in a setting where all students are taught together. However, some teachers are still having trouble finding teaching materials that fit the needs of the most recent learning platform (Efriana, 2021).

According to Pocaan (2022) collaboration between mainstream and support teacher's specifically special education teachers (SpEd) can help to address these issues. Jarl et al. (2021) suggested that for profession to be successful, teachers must be effective collaborators. Because educational advances would otherwise encourage teacher collaboration, refusing to cooperate is no longer an option (Jacobs & Renandya, 2019). Thus, providing instruction to many student groups, including those with special needs, in a general educational setting, in a flexible style, and meeting learning needs is known as inclusive education (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2020). Lehane & Senior (2020) noted that mainstream teachers and special education teachers collaborate in this sector. Here, the abilities of these educators can be evaluated to gauge their knowledge, disposition, and level of preparedness for the difficulties presented by this system (Sailor et al., 2021). Collaborative teaching is considered a new variation of the traditional team-teaching model, typically characterized as involving two general education teachers working together to meet the needs of a particular group of students (Aliakbari & Valizadeh (2023). In the co-teaching model, the general educator and special educator share different, but complementary knowledge and skills as they work together to meet the diverse needs of students (Sundqvist et al., 2021).

Moreover, Zulfikar & Aulia (2020) emphasized that collaborative teaching allows teachers to pool their knowledge and expertise, resulting in a more comprehensive and effective learning experience for students. Students are exposed to different teaching styles and perspectives, which can help them better understand and retain the material (Anthonysamy et al., 2020). Collaborative teaching enables teachers to learn from one another, share ideas and resources, and develop their teaching skills (Baguma et al., 2019). Teachers can gain new insights and ideas, and expand their knowledge base through collaboration. Collaborative teaching can help teachers manage their classrooms more effectively by sharing responsibilities and strategies. Teachers can work together to create a positive and supportive learning environment, which can enhance student engagement and motivation (Chiu, 2021).

Collaborative Teaching

According to Huang Et al., (2021) collaborative teaching is an approach to teaching where two or more teachers work together to plan, teach, and evaluate a lesson or series of lessons. The aim is to combine the strengths and expertise of each teacher to provide a more comprehensive and effective learning experience for students (Baier et al., 2019). Collaborative teaching can take many forms, such as co-

teaching, team teaching, or collaborative planning (Marzocchi et al., 2021). In co-teaching, two teachers share responsibility for the same class or group of students and work together to plan and deliver instruction (Hermoza, 2022). In team teaching, two or more teachers work together to teach different subjects or aspects of a subject. Collaborative planning involves teachers working together to plan a lesson or series of lessons, with each teacher contributing their expertise in a particular area (Ogegbo et al., 2019). Collaborative teaching has several benefits for both teachers and students. Teachers can share the workload, gain new insights and ideas, and develop their skills by working with colleagues (Lei & Medwell, 2021). Students benefit from the varied teaching styles and perspectives of multiple teachers, which can help them to better understand and retain the material (Mahmood, 2021). Collaborative teaching can also help to create a more positive and supportive learning environment for students. To implement collaborative teaching successfully, teachers should establish clear goals and roles, communicate effectively, and be open to feedback and constructive criticism (Mofield, 2020).

In addition, it is commonly believed that education provides learners with the necessary framework for acquiring collaborative skills before joining the profession (Fisher et al., 2020). Pelletier et al., (2022) noted that collaboration among educators is essential for turning learners into future experts. Teachers demonstrate cooperative learning for their students by working together as a team. Special education teachers help craft the lessons for inclusive classrooms to ensure that the needs of students with disabilities are considered. It is especially concerning that the mainstream teacher and SpEd are fully aware of the problem given the growing difficulties in our country's educational system. Every special education teacher will face this problem at some point in their careers. To implement blended learning and gradually move to face-to-face classes, which is forcing SPED teachers and other teachers to think of different ways to adapt to the change, we will look at how teachers from different fields can work together to deal with the challenges and stress that come with these changes. Teachers could work together to make a curriculum that all students can follow, or the special education teacher could make changes to the lesson plans of the general education teacher.

In Talisay City, where the researcher is currently teaching inclusive education, most of the mainstream teachers are currently struggling to find ways to adapt to have adequate competencies in teaching students with special educational needs (LSENs) especially face to face classes was implemented. There is no denying that the ability to target the specific needs of these children is very important, especially as they mix with regular students. Mainstream teachers who have opportunities handling learners with special educational needs (LSENs) are likely to have different specific needs for how to best implement their teaching in these situations. At the same time, special

education teachers are adjusting to this current concern by acquiring competencies to better handle learners in inclusive education because learners have been studying at home for more than two years. Therefore, the researcher can see the need for collaboration with each other to be more prepared and have enough competencies to ease any test caused by the reopening of the school in the current face-to-face implementation.

The primary goal of this study is to determine the perception of collaborative teaching by special education teachers and mainstream teachers with learners with special needs (LSENs) in an inclusive education setting, specifically at identified public schools at Talisay City as they transition from blended learning to face-to-face learning. Also, this study is significant because it helps teachers understand the significance of collaboration in an inclusive education that will work best for their teaching and learning styles as they transition from blended learning to face-to-face instruction by identifying potential effective strategies and instructions.

Results and Discussions

Table 1. SPED Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Knowledge

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I was briefed on the implementation of inclusive education before it is carried out.	3.22	Positive
2	I am directly involved in meetings on inclusive education at school.	3.11	Positive
3	I was given detailed explanation on the concepts and goals of inclusive education	3.22	Positive
4	I should be provided with a letter from DepEd regarding inclusive education as a guide	3.11	Positive
5	I should be supplied with the Inclusive Education Program Guidelines from DepEd as reference.	3.22	Positive
6	I was given an Inclusive teaching schedule	2.78	Positive
7	I should have been exposed to the teaching method required in the Inclusive class.	2.89	Positive
8	I was given a comprehensive picture on strengths and weaknesses of the students in inclusive classroom	2.89	Positive
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.06	Positive

Table 1 displays the level of perception of SPED teachers about collaboration in inclusive education in terms of knowledge is "Positive" with aggregated weighted mean of 3.06. This depicts that that the SPED teachers who are currently in inclusive education have enough knowledge of the method to keep up in terms of teaching. It also shows

teachers there is positive perception regarding collaboration and necessary information regarding inclusive education. For the knowledge aspect, it clearly shows from statement “I was given detailed explanation on the concepts and goals of inclusive education” and I was briefed on the implementation of inclusive education before it is carried out “both obtained the weighted mean of 3.22 or “Positive” is at the high level. It shows SPED teacher being ready to be included in inclusive education where they will interact with mainstream teachers. According to the study of Razalli et.al (2020) explained that the level of teachers' knowledge should be further enhanced to maximize concerns in inclusive education, which proves special education teachers lack knowledge about subject content to be taught to mainstream students. In addition, Ripley (2021) discussed "the ideas of differentiated instruction, multiple learning styles, group instruction, weekly reviews, and detailed planning that directly benefit students. Teachers must receive preparation and support in the classroom. It is also crucial that planning time be continuously available throughout the school year. Students immediately benefit from the principles of tailored instruction that teachers, especially SPED teachers, need to understand. It's critical that SPED teachers receive training and assistance in the classroom. Additionally, it is crucial that dissemination of knowledge in inclusive education is routinely offered throughout the academic year.

Table 2. Mainstream Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Knowledge

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I was briefed on the implementation of inclusive education before it is carried out.	3.50	Very Positive
2	I am directly involved in meetings on inclusive education at school.	3.00	Positive
3	I was given detailed explanation on the concepts and goals of inclusive education	3.30	Very Positive
4	I should be provided with a letter from DepEd regarding inclusive education as a guide	3.40	Very Positive
5	I should be supplied with the Inclusive Education Program Guidelines from DepEd as reference.	3.60	Very Positive
6	I was given an Inclusive teaching schedule	2.70	Positive
7	I should have been exposed to the teaching method required in the Inclusive class.	3.70	Very Positive
8	I was given a comprehensive picture on strengths and weaknesses of the students in inclusive classroom	2.80	Positive
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.25	Very Positive

Table 2 shows that the level of perception of mainstream teachers about collaboration in inclusive education in terms of knowledge is “Very

Positive" with an aggregated weighted mean of 3.25. The result clearly shows that perception of mainstream teachers in an inclusive education in terms of knowledge have background already how to handle learners with special educational needs (LSENs). The primary objective of inclusive education in today's culture especially now that face to face classes were implemented in the country is to provide all students with access to a high-quality education while taking into account their specific needs. Because of this learner with special educational needs (LSENs) can socialize and are protected from prejudice and limitations due of their special needs thanks to inclusive education (Rogers W. & Johnson N., 2018). Therefore, in order to meet unique demands and expedite the delivery of suitable instructional guidance, mainstream teachers must possess the necessary understanding to manage LSENs in the classroom which was clearly demonstrated in statements 1, 3, 8. Moreover, in statement 7: "I should have been introduced to the teaching technique required in the inclusive class," the result demonstrates that the mainstream teachers had the necessary abilities which was very necessary for them to acquire to be effective in handling learners with special educational needs (LSENs) in an inclusive education settings. Therefore, the knowledge required to manage students with special educational needs (LSENs) is shared, mainstream teachers view collaboration in this study as very favorable.

Table 3. SPED Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Attitude

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I feel collaboration is impossible in finding new skills and real competition will take place.	2.67	Positive
2	I believe that collaboration is necessary for everyone to achieve shared goals	3.56	Very Positive
3	I believe that students will obtain good achievement through collaboration with other teachers in teaching.	3.56	Very Positive
4	When I collaborate, I can hardly share my teaching experience.	3.00	Positive
5	I need more effort to collaborate with teachers involved in inclusive education	2.67	Positive
6	In reality, all teachers can work alone and do not feel the need for joint teaching with other teachers to teach in the Inclusive class.	1.78	Negative
7	I think collaborative teaching is just a waste of time.	1.67	Very Negative
8	It's good for me to work alone in teaching.	1.78	Negative
9	I think teaching together will provide opportunities for mainstream teachers and Special Education teachers	3.56	Very Positive
10	I believe that teaching together in the classroom will give more efficient support to students, especially to special students.	3.44	Very Positive
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.77	Positive

Table 3 displays that the level of perception of SPED teachers towards collaboration towards inclusive education is “Positive” with aggregate weighted mean of 2.27. This depicts that the collaboration between mainstream teachers produces excellent outcomes, and that SPED teachers have a favorable outlook on inclusive education. Item nos.2, 3 and 9 had the highest mean of 3.56 in terms of attitude. Similar studies have been done by Ghedin and Aquario (2020), who found that teachers' attitudes are crucial to collaborative teaching practice. Their work demonstrates the good attitude special education teachers and mainstream teachers share when working together. Additionally, personality is cited by Shin, Lee, and McKenna (2016) as a significant barrier to co-teaching in inclusive education. In order to properly implement inclusive education, mainstream teachers must successfully collaborate and fulfill their obligations. According to the study of Kramer et.al (2018) the dependency or interdependence between the teachers and his or her collaboration partner is a popular method to characterize collaboration and the level of collaboration between teachers according to little in the early 1990s from this is a characteristic of the type of collaboration. Hence, Understanding SPED teachers' attitudes is critical to the development and success of collaborative teaching practices in an inclusive education (Mora-Ruano et.al, 2018).

Table 4. Mainstream Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Attitude

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I feel collaboration is impossible in finding new skills and real competition will take place.	3.30	Very Positive
2	I believe that collaboration is necessary	3.80	Very Positive
3	I believe that students will obtain good achievement through collaboration with other teachers in teaching.	3.80	Very Positive
4	When I collaborate, I can hardly share my teaching experience.	3.20	Positive
5	I need more effort to collaborate with teachers involved in inclusive education and it is a difficult process for me.	3.30	Very Positive
6	In reality, all teachers can work alone and do not feel the need for joint teaching with other teachers	2.60	Positive
7	Collaborative teaching is just a waste of time.	2.30	Negative
8	It's good for me to work alone in teaching.	2.20	Negative
9	I think teaching together will provide opportunities for mainstream teachers and Special Education teachers	3.70	Very Positive
10	I believe that teaching together in the classroom will give more efficient support to students, especially to special students.	3.80	Very Positive
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.20	Positive

Table 4 demonstrates the level of perception of mainstream teachers towards collaboration in inclusive education in terms of attitude is “Positive” with aggregate weighted mean of 3.20. This implies mainstream teachers views collaboration as positive that impacts the way they accept the challenges of inclusive education, an opportunity to increase their competencies in handling learners with special educational needs (LSEs). The mainstream teachers reported that, ideally, collaborative teaching had many positive aspects, such as open and communication between SPED teachers, recognition of each other as partners of equal importance for the learners with special educational needs (LSEs), and the feeling of being able to move around freely in the inclusive classroom which demonstrate in item no. 10. This study is supported by Pancsofar & Petroff (2016), who demonstrate that teachers who engage in cooperative teaching experiences will have more positive attitudes than those who do not. This study, however, demonstrates that educators who have negative views about collaborative teaching are less likely to use it as a teaching technique. According to conventional knowledge in education, one instructor should take the reins while the other observes in an inclusive classroom (Pancsofar & Petroff, 2016). Therefore, mainstream teachers’ perception towards collaboration in their works proves will not only bring benefit to teachers but also to learners in an inclusive education.

Table 5. SPED Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Readiness

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I was given enough space and time to interact with mainstream / special education teachers.	3.00	Positive
2	Collaborative teaching is a professional experience that is very valuable to me	3.22	Positive
3	I am willing to share my expertise on providing special needs learning module.	3.44	Very Positive
4	I accept the presence of other teachers in the classroom during the learning process.	3.22	Positive
5	I am willing to change my teaching techniques and strategies to ensure that students with special needs can easily understand.	3.56	Very Positive
6	I am willing to be an active teacher if given the opportunity to teach together.	3.44	Very Positive
7	I am willing to teach together again if given the opportunity.	3.44	Very Positive
8	I am willing to share the results with current special teachers / mainstream teachers when teaching students with special needs in the Inclusive class.	3.44	Very Positive
9	I am willing to take turn in teaching with other teachers in my class.	3.33	Very Positive
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.35	Very Positive

Table 5 shows the level of perception of SPED teachers in terms of Readiness which is “Very Positive” with aggregate weighted mean of

3.35. This illustrates that the perception of SPED teachers is fully prepared in handling learners with special educational needs (LSENs) in an inclusive education. Teachers can overcome the challenges of teaching in inclusive classrooms by working together with SPED and mainstream teachers. For the aspect of readiness, the item no. 5 with the highest mean of 3.56 is “I am willing to change my teaching techniques and strategies to ensure that students with special needs can easily understand “at high level. Whereas the item no.1 with the lowest mean of 3.00 which is “I was given enough space and time to interact with mainstream / special education teachers” is at moderate level. It was found that the overall perception of teachers in terms of readiness of teachers to collaborate in an inclusive education is at high. This means that SPED teachers who are involved in inclusive education are better prepared to teach together in an inclusive class. The results are comparable to those of the Razalli et al. (2020) study, which demonstrates that teachers are highly prepared to change their methods of instruction in order to better comprehend children with special needs. While a linked study to the work done in Washington in 2022 shows that teachers who collaborate in the classroom will have a more favorable view than teachers who are not active in collaborative teaching.

Table 6. Mainstream Teachers about Collaboration in Inclusive Education in terms of Readiness

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I was given enough space and time to interact with mainstream / special education teachers.	3.20	Positive
2	Collaborative teaching is a professional experience that is very valuable to me	3.40	Very Positive
3	I am willing to share my expertise on providing special needs learning module.	3.40	Very Positive
4	I accept the presence of other teachers in the classroom during the learning process.	3.40	Very Positive
5	I am willing to change my teaching techniques and strategies to ensure that students with special needs can easily understand.	3.40	Very Positive
6	I am willing to be an active teacher if given the opportunity to teach together.	3.40	Very Positive
7	I am willing to teach together again if given the opportunity.	3.40	Very Positive
8	I am willing to share the results with current special teachers / mainstream teachers when teaching students with special needs in the Inclusive class.	3.40	Very Positive
9	I am willing to take turn in teaching with other teachers in my class.	3.50	Very Positive
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.39	Very Positive

Table 6 shows the level of perception of mainstream teachers towards collaboration as “Very Positive” with an aggregate weighted mean of

3.39. Majority of items obtained weighted mean of 3.40 while item no.9 “I am willing to take turn in teaching with other teachers in my class” ranked as the highest of 3.50 or “Very Positive” showed that teachers in mainstream ready to accept changes related to collaboration to maintain positive relationship between coworkers that will results in effective co teaching. For Kelly (2018) expressed that compared to other settings, teachers can learn more about teaching in the same classroom. In the fulfillment level, teachers are treated equally in the classroom. Co teachers can achieve equality by collaborating and working together to achieve common goals.

Table 7. Test of significant difference between the perception of SPED and mainstream teachers about collaboration in inclusive education

Variables	Source of Difference	Mean	sd	Mean Diff.	Comp. t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Knowledge	SPED Teachers	24.44	3.40	-1.56	-0.972	0.345	Accept Ho	NS
	Mainstream Teachers	26.00	3.56					
Attitude	SPED Teachers	27.67	2.69	-4.33	-2.153	0.503	Accept Ho	NS
	Mainstream Teachers	32.00	5.70					
Readiness	SPED Teachers	30.11	4.17	-0.39	-0.214	0.833	Accept Ho	NS
	Mainstream Teachers	30.50	3.75					

*Significant at $p < 0.05$; NS = Not Significant; S = Significant

The following are the computed statistics for the relationship of the two variables: knowledge ($\chi^2 = -1.56$, $p=0.972$), attitude ($\chi^2 = -4.33$, $p= -2.153$), readiness ($\chi^2 = -0.39$, $p= -0.214$). The results revealed that the p-values for knowledge, attitude and readiness are less than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) which indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. Based on the findings, there is no significant difference in the perception of SPED and mainstream teachers about collaboration in inclusive education in terms of knowledge, attitude, and readiness. Recent study of Byrd, D. R. & Alexander, M. (2020) “Investigating special education teachers’ knowledge and skills: Preparing general teacher preparation for professional development” the highlights the significance of information and viewpoints on collaboration, but there is no obvious connection between the two at the level of the teacher's opinion of collaboration. Besides, the study of Jorveit and Kovac (2022) explained

that the findings demonstrate that successful collaboration is fostered through training that incorporates inclusive education and a fundamental awareness of diversity. Collaboration such as co teaching situations are more successful for teachers with practice and professional backgrounds when educational specialists who wish to be more intimate with one another are involved. Therefore, collaboration teaching of teachers in inclusive education plays a significant role in education that needs to develop and enhance more the specifics element the knowledge, attitude and readiness.

Discussion

The study suggests that the Department of Education and school administration structure the school timetable to accommodate periods for teacher collaborative activities and training because it has been discovered that teacher collaboration as a method of professional development improves perceptions of inclusive education. This will make it possible for teachers who work with both SPED and mainstream students to get together, talk about their strengths and challenges, and find solutions as a group. Additionally, it is advised that school administrators support teacher collaboration by creating a supportive environment and organizing the necessary resources. Study also revealed that knowledge, attitude and readiness is not a significant factor that affects both teachers as to how they perceive collaboration in inclusive education. However, these data prompt to teachers the importance of collaborative teaching to the belief that it will improve the quality of teaching and learning in an inclusive education.

Conclusion

This study examined the perception among SPED and mainstream about collaboration with knowledge, attitude and readiness as moderating variable. This also entails providing teachers with a proper orientation to inclusive education, along with the knowledge that can aid enable teaching alongside mainstream educators. Weather teacher's attitude and readiness revealed has a positive perception towards collaboration. Also, these results justify motivating collaboration between SPED and general education teachers at the classroom level. Teachers can raise their own standards by cooperating with one another. They will be able to get together and exchange teaching techniques and knowledge hurdles, their own as well as the students'. Additionally, given that face-to-face instruction is already in place and is expected in schools, this will give them the ability to improve their knowledge, skills, and readiness while assuring their success in their teaching efforts in an inclusive environment.

References

- Agaton, C. B., & Cueto, L. J. (2021). Learning at Home: Parents' Lived Experiences on Distance Learning during COVID-19 Pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 901-911.
- Aliakbari, M., & Valizadeh, P. (2023). Exploring identity construction in team teaching: The case of Iranian student-teachers. *Cogent Education*, 10(1), 2168934.
- Ariyanto, S. (2018). A portrait of gender bias in the prescribed Indonesian ELT textbook for junior high school students. *Sexuality & Culture*, 22, 1054–1076. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12119-018-9512-8>
- Anthonyamy, L., Koo, A. C., & Hew, S. H. (2020). Self-regulated learning strategies and non-academic outcomes in higher education blended learning environments: A one decade review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25, 3677-3704.
- Baguma, R., Bagarukayo, E., Namubiru, P., Brown, C., & Mayisela, T. (2019). Using WhatsApp in Teaching to Develop Higher Order Thinking Skills--A Literature Review Using the Activity Theory Lens. *International Journal of Education and Development Using Information and Communication Technology*, 15(2), 98-116.
- Baier, F., Decker, A. T., Voss, T., Kleickmann, T., Klusmann, U., & Kunter, M. (2019). What makes a good teacher? The relative importance of mathematics teachers' cognitive ability, personality, knowledge, beliefs, and motivation for instructional quality. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 89(4), 767-786.
- Brem, A., Viardot, E., & Nylund, P. A. (2021). Implications of the coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak for innovation: Which technologies will improve our lives? *Technological forecasting and social change*, 163, 120451.
- Byrd, D. R., & Alexander, M. (2020). Investigating special education teachers' knowledge and skills: Preparing general teacher preparation for professional development. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 4(2), 72-82.
- Chiu, T. K. (2021). Student engagement in K-12 online learning amid COVID-19: A qualitative approach from a self-determination theory perspective. *Interactive learning environments*, 1-14.
- Efriana, L. (2021). Problems of online learning during COVID-19 pandemic in EFL classroom and the solution. *JELITA*, 38-47.
- Fischer, G., Lundin, J., & Lindberg, J. O. (2020). Rethinking and reinventing learning, education and collaboration in the digital age— from creating technologies to transforming cultures. *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 37(5), 241-252.
- Ghedini, E., & Aquario, D. (2020). Collaborative teaching in mainstream schools: Research with general education and support teachers. *International Journal of Whole Schooling*, 16(2), 1-34

- Graham, L. J., White, S. L. J., Cologon, K., & Pianta, R. C. (2020). Do teachers' years of experience make a difference in the quality of teaching? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 96, 103190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103190>
- Hermoza, A. L. (2022). Successful Co-Teaching Models in the Secondary Setting.
- Huang, X., Lai, M. Y., & Huang, R. (2021). Teachers' learning through an online lesson study: an analysis from the expansive learning perspective. *International Journal for Lesson & Learning Studies*.
- Lehane, P., & Senior, J. (2020). Collaborative teaching: exploring the impact of co-teaching practices on the numeracy attainment of pupils with and without special educational needs. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 35(3), 303-317.
- Lei, M., & Medwell, J. (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on student teachers: How the shift to online collaborative learning affects student teachers' learning and future teaching in a Chinese context. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 22, 169-179.
- Jarl, M., Andersson, K., & Blossing, U. (2021). Organizational characteristics of successful and failing schools: A theoretical framework for explaining variation in student achievement. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 32(3), 448-464.
- Jacobs, G. M., & Renandya, W. A. (2019). *Student centered cooperative learning: Linking concepts in education to promote student learning*. Springer.
- Kelly, A. (2018). Co-teaching in higher education: Reflections from an early career academic. *Journal of Learning and Teaching in Higher Education*, 1(2), 181-188. <https://doi.org/10.29311/jlthe.v1i2.2798>
- Krammer, M., Rossmann, P., Gastager, A., & Gasteiger-Klicpera, B. (2018). Ways of composing teaching teams and their impact on teachers' perceptions about collaboration. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(4), 463-478.
- Marzocchi, A. S., Druken, B. K., & Brye, M. V. (2021). Careful Co-Planning for Effective Team Teaching in Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 16(3), em0663.
- Mahmood, S. (2021). Instructional strategies for online teaching in COVID-19 pandemic. *Human behavior and emerging technologies*, 3(1), 199-203.
- Mofield, E. L. (2020). Benefits and barriers to collaboration and co-teaching: Examining perspectives of gifted education teachers and general education teachers. *Gifted Child Today*, 43(1), 20-33.
- Mora-Ruano, J.G., Gebhardt, M., & Wittmann, E. (2018). Teacher collaboration in German schools: Do gender and school type influence the frequency of collaboration among teachers? *Frontiers in Education*,

3, Article 55, 1-12. Mulholland, M. & O'Connor, U. (2016). Collaborative classroom practice for teaching.

Ogegbo, A. A., Gaigher, E., & Salagaram, T. (2019). Benefits and challenges of lesson study: A case of teaching Physical Sciences in South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(1).

Paulsrud, D., & Nilholm, C. (2020). Teaching for inclusion—a review of research on the cooperation between regular teachers and special educators in the work with students in need of special support. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1-15.

Pelletier, K., McCormack, M., Reeves, J., Robert, J., Arbino, N., Dickson-Deane, C., ... & Stine, J. (2022). *2022 EDUCAUSE Horizon Report Teaching and Learning Edition* (pp. 1-58). EDUC22.

Pocan, J. M. (2022). Exploring teaching strategies and challenges towards a holistic context-based special education teaching strategies program. *The Normal Lights*, 16(1), 29.

Razalli, A. R., Hashim, A. T., Mamat, N., & Ariffin, A. (2020). Collaborative Teaching between Special Education Teachers and Mainstream Teachers in Inclusive Education Program. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 10(8), 1055-1065

Sailor, W., Skrtic, T. M., Cohn, M., & Olmstead, C. (2021). Preparing teacher educators for statewide scale-up of multi-tiered system of support (MTSS). *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 44(1), 24-41.

Sundqvist, C., Björk-Åman, C., & Ström, K. (2021). Co-teaching during teacher training periods: experiences of Finnish special education and general education teacher candidates. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 1-15.

Surot, L. (2019, March 22). Capacity-Building of Receiving Teachers in Handling Learners with Special Educational Needs Through SPED-LAC. TeacherPH. <https://www.teacherph.com/handling-learners-with-special-educational-needs/>

Tarrayo, V.N., Potestades, R.R. & Ulla, M.B. Exploring the Gender Perspective in English Language Teaching (ELT): Voices from ELT Practitioners in Philippine Higher Education Institutions. *Sexuality & Culture* 25, 1634–1652 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12119-021-09840-x>

Zulfikar, Z., & Aulia, C. T. (2020). Exploring Acehese EFL College Students' Perceptions on Collaborative Writing. *Wanastra: Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra*, 12(2), 171-180.